

THE COMBAT AGAINST NARCOMANIA AS ENSURING A HEALTHY LIFE IN SOCIETY**Huseynov Tofiq***Lecturer of the chair "Legal Studies"
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The narcomania scourge, which has been spread in society as "white death", causes incurable complications in people's lives that are difficult to treat. This disaster, which is terrifying for humanity, has become one of the most problematic issues, making all peoples and nations think deeply, regardless of their race, age or religion. Narcomania has taken many people in its aura as a terrible disaster. Narcomania, including narcotism, is on the same level with the other most dangerous problems, such as arms trafficking, human trafficking and the transfer of human organs and has become a global and dangerous issue at the international level.

Keywords: terrorism, drug, narcomania, narcotism, narco trafficking, narco business

As one of the important steps that serves to solve this problem, the increase and expansion of educational work among teenagers and young people have been in the spotlight as a priority. Taking into account the risk of the spread of drugs among the young generation, a number of countries have adopted national state programs "For a future without drugs" in the field of combating it. This also demonstrates that citizens live in healthy, safe conditions and the development of society. Compliance with the national program should be valued as the duty of every citizen. This program includes enlightenment campaigns about the consequences of drug addiction in education, health care, law enforcement and other organizations, its indelible scars, ways to get rid of it, etc. The events held under the state program were covered in the mass media and posted on the Internet. This is the main commitment imposed on the executors. It is known that June 26 was declared by the United Nations as the "International Day Against Drug Addiction and Drug Business" in order to keep the global community constantly focused on this scourge, which is considered dangerous for humanity. In this regard, all relevant institutions have drawn up plans for holding a number of events and directed them to their implementation. It was the step taken on June 26 in connection with the fight against drug addiction that was evaluated as a report. When all the works carried out give their positive results, conditions are created for them to work more efficiently and realize them from the direction of the optimal approach, with a number of tasks defined in order to determine the prospects for future implementation in practice. Anti-drug measures implemented in the field of the formation of a genetically healthy generation in our society, which is considered the main task in the main political strategy of the state of Azerbaijan, are not a campaign but are constantly in the spotlight, becoming the main and continuous policy of our state. It is considered as a common human scourge [8,9].

Here, every citizen of the country must reveal his moral obligation with honor and conscience. Because when the fight against drug addiction is carried out in an organized form rather than individually, it can make its positive contributions faster.

On August 26, 1996, a new stage was entered by signing a decree by the great leader Heydar Aliyev regarding the fight against drug addiction, including the illegal circulation of drugs, as a national duty. This decree included a number of features [2]. Based on the requirements arising from the content of the decree, a National State Program was prepared and a commission was created for the purpose of combating the spread of drug addiction, narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and their precursors within the time frame that is ahead, i.e. until the year 2000. On June 18, 1999, the Milli Majlis of the Republic of Azerbaijan adopted the law "On combating the illegal circulation of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances, as well as their precursors" [3]. The general purpose of adopting these documents is to prohibit the planting of narcotic plants in Azerbaijan, their cultivation, and the production of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, including their precursors [9]. For this purpose, the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan was adopted in 2000. Chapter 26 of Section X of the Code describes crimes under this designation. Articles 234-241 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan reflect violations of this series [6]. In the disposition of those substances, notes were made about the rules of use of narcotic drugs in excess of personal consumption amount, its sale, share and compensation, etc. Liabilities for violating the rules stipulated in the sanction of those articles are also indicated. The main goal of this law is to adapt people to civil society and a healthy social environment. Decision No. 191 dated October 12, 2000 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan was adopted to determine the amount of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances intended for personal consumption [12]. In that decision, the list and quantity of prohibited narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances were reflected.

It is a pity that drug addiction remains a serious issue in our republic. A number of our young people have become addicted to drugs and are currently rolling in that vortex, which causes them to fall under the influence of the Criminal Code described above [1]. Citizens falling under the sphere of influence become the subjects of that law, they are responsible for the violations they have committed. As a result, they are isolated

from society and placed in penal institutions and medical institutions for treatment. The increase in crimes from this series increases its social danger in the dynamics of crimes. The increase in the number of drug addicts puts the national gene pool under serious threat.

It is an undeniable scourge that the whole world is currently suffering from the illegal cycle of drugs. This puts people under serious threat. Drug addiction leads to an increase in crime. So, a number of crimes are committed under the influence of drugs. For example: intentional homicide - a person commits the act under the influence of drugs. A person commits thefts, robberies and crimes to obtain drugs. The beginnings of a number of diseases are laid in people under the influence of drug addiction. They suffer seriously from a psychological point of view, they cannot adapt to society. They face problems in the treatment of social society, which leads to their moral degradation. It acts as a source of danger for the society by creating the basis for the expansion and increase of a number of negative rhesus in the society.

As the social danger of drug addiction increases, the need to fight it in society becomes even more inevitable, that is, it becomes a more urgent issue. Cases of drug use and its illegal circulation have become a global problem, expanding further in recent years. This instills a negative impact on the rule of law, economy, social environment and state policy.

Victims of drug addiction are mostly weak-willed, teenagers and young people. A drug addict becomes a great tragedy for himself, his family and loved ones. In other words, the presence of addiction leads to aggravation of their health from a physical point of view.

Victims of drug addiction first lose their self-esteem, then their moral qualities, and then their mental balance. Due to medical criteria, they cannot communicate with their family and loved ones, they cannot adapt to any occupation, they even forget what they were able to do before they fell into drug addiction. They always bring unhappiness, despair, distrust to those around them. That is, they have an abnormal psyche [10].

During the studies, it was determined that when people use drugs, they first feel good, they think that joy, energy, and the success they can achieve are caused by those substances and they try to convince themselves of this. Of course, this thought and feeling is completely wrong. If this were true, people who have achieved great success in life would owe everything to drugs [11].

When interviewing addicts, it can be concluded that family and work problems, psychological weakness and other problems lead them astray. Of course, those who do it purely for fun are the overwhelming majority.

I would like to note with sadness that the vast majority of drug users are young people. This is a very scary factor because the young generation is the main pillar of our nation and state. If there is a drug addict in the family, the vast majority of babies who open their eyes to the world are born with defects. According to experts, young people who take the first step in family life must undergo a medical examination, because this

is a solid foundation for the development of this young generation.

It should be noted that drug addiction not only affects the health of mankind, but also the entire world economy through drug trafficking. Along with the increase in criminality, the illegal circulation of drugs poses a serious threat to international security, as well as the financial base of terrorism. It becomes the main financial sector of the concept of terrorism, increasing its financial budget.

Experts estimate that hundreds of billions of dollars are earned during the year due to the illegal circulation of narcotic substances. Even according to the estimates of the UN Office on Drugs and Crime, drugs are the third most profitable industry in the world. Millions of people suffer from it. If this happens in the future, this trend will lead to a public disaster. The worst thing is that drug addiction among young people is increasing rapidly.

Another danger of drug addiction is that it creates irreversibility in a pathological state in people. That is, even during treatment, complications remain in some organs of people forever. That is, if people who have stayed away from bad habits for a long time take decisive steps to live high in their brains, they fall back into the hell of drugs. Doctors note that. There is no recovered drug addict, there is an inactive drug addict, that is, there is a concept of a citizen who does not use drugs. They prefer this concept. Some people develop a mental disorder as a result of the drug's effects, which remains unchanged for life.

Drug addicts leave people crippled physically as well as mentally. By lowering the level of immunity in people, it leads to complications in the cardiovascular system, kidneys, liver and other organs. In the end, as the body weakens, a person loses weight, physical strength is gradually depleted, and death becomes a reality. Research shows that the life expectancy of drug addicts from adolescence, as well as from early times, is between 35 and 40 years.

Currently, 250 million inhabitants of our planet suffer from drugs. This information is reflected in the report prepared by the World Health Organization. In that report, it was mentioned that 47 million of drug victims are in Latin America, 1,200,000 in Mexico, 750,000 in the European Union countries, more than 26 million in the CIS and Asian countries, etc. Experts note that this figure does not reflect the full reality, that is, more than half of drug addicts are not registered. Compared to other countries, drug addiction exists on a large scale in our country, and combating it is one of the main policies of the state [7].

After gaining its independence, our country has taken a number of targeted and urgent steps related to the illegal circulation of drugs along with all areas.

In order to prevent the preparation of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and precursors and their raw materials, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Mr. Ilham Aliyev issued a number of orders. So, in this regard, the state program was approved in 2000-2006, 2007-2012, 2013-2018. Currently, the next 5-year State Program covering the years 2019-2024 has been approved and directed for implementation by the

Decree of President Ilham Aliyev dated July 22, 2019 regarding the illegal circulation of drugs [4]. This gives the reason that all the steps taken against the illegal circulation of drugs are one of the main priorities of the state, and the uncompromising position in this regard is always in the center of attention.

In our country, the entire strategy in the field of combating drug addiction is being implemented with great success, decisive steps are being taken against the background of young people living in a healthy environment and being educated. Because those who do not think about today cannot have a future.

References

1. Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan. November 12, 1995.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated August 26, 1996 on the illegal circulation of narcotics.
3. Law of June 18, 1999 on the fight against the illegal circulation of narcotics and psychotropic substances.
4. 5-year state program related to the illegal cycle of narcotic drugs covering the years 2019-2024: decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated July 22, 2019.
5. Allahverdiyeva, Kh. Drug addiction is not just injecting - it is a way of life [Text] / Kh. Allahverdiyeva // Law.- 1999.- №5-6.- P.116.
6. Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan: Section X, Chapter XXVI, Article 234-241. Baku 2000.
7. On accession to the United Nations Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs (December 1, 1998, No. 550-IQ)
8. On the circulation of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and their precursors (June 28, 2005, No. 959-IIQ)
9. On the approval of the lists of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances sufficient to bring a person to criminal responsibility, as well as their total amount (June 28, 2005, No. 961-IIQ)
10. On amending the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On the circulation of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and their precursors" (October 1, 2007, No. 418-IIIQD)
11. On the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On the circulation of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and their precursors" (August 9, 2005, No. 280)
12. Decision No. 191 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the AR dated October 12, 2000 on the quantity of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances intended for personal consumption.